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Multidimensional inequalities among adolescent girls and women living with or at risk of HIV in Nigeria and South Africa

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Aim

This study aimed to investigate the multiple dimensions of HIV-related inequality faced by women and girls living with HIV.

Methods

Between June and November 2021, two cross-sectional surveys were conducted collaboratively with community-based organisations in Nigeria and South Africa. We adopted Sen's capability approach of inequality and selected relevant measures of inequality in the capabilities of women and girls living with HIV to i) live a healthy life, ii) live in physical safety and legal security, iii) be knowledgeable, iv) achieve economic independence, v) have secure living conditions; vi) enjoy individual, family and social life, and to have self-respect, and vii) participate in decision-making, have a voice and influence. We performed descriptive statistical analysis per HIV status and country. We additionally calculated the Gini coefficient, Lorenz curve, location (means) and dispersion (standard deviation) of key markers.

Results

We found significant discrepancies across all the dimensions of inequality. Women and girls living with HIV reported lower physical and mental health, poorer access to healthcare and capability to meet basic needs. In addition, they had weaker economic independence, lower rates of tertiary education and faced more precarity than HIV-negative women and girls though at high risk of HIV. Furthermore, HIV-positive women and girls were confronted with more sexual and gender-based violence and suffered from stigma and discrimination, particularly among adolescent girls and young women. Ultimately, women living with HIV reported lower life satisfaction compared to their HIV-negative counterparts.

Figure 1: Lorenz curve of inequality in subjective well-being per HIV serostatus in Nigeria and South Africa

Conclusions

The multidimensional approach to inequality shows how HIV status amplifies existing inequalities in multiple life dimensions for women and girls in Nigeria and South Africa. It underscores the need for multifaceted interventions to address inequalities in all aspects of the life of African women and girls, with context-specific empowerment programmes increasing their capability to live the life they want.